

Entrance window test bench trials

Introduction

S³-LEB (Super Separator Spectrometer – Low Energy Branch) is a facility under construction at GANIL which will implement an IGLIS (In Gas-cell Laser Ionization Spectroscopy) based technique for the study of exotic nuclei. In this setup, the S³ will be coupled to the linear accelerator of the SPIRAL-2 facility of GANIL. Fusion evaporation reaction products will be separated and selected from the primary beam and other contaminants by the S³ to enter a gas cell/gas jet setup. The gas cell/ gas jet positions at the focal plane of the S³ where radioactive ion beams from the S³ will then enter through an entrance window to be thermalized and neutralized in the gas cell and In-gas cell/ In-gas jet laser spectroscopy can be performed.

For different physics cases at S³-LEB, entrance window materials considered for the gas cell are Titanium and Mylar foils. The window should provide sufficient gas-vacuum separation as well as possess good stopping power. The materials for the entrance window are chosen such that there is low attenuation of the S³ beams as the ions enter the gas cell. The stopping cross section width of the gas cell is 30 mm. The gas cell entrance has a diameter of 50 mm. The S³ side of the gas cell is at vacuum and the other side is at 200-500 mbar Ar pressure. For low Z-values essentially, deceleration of the ion beam would be less. Aluminium would be a good choice in this aspect but it easily breaks when made thinner. The fragileness of the foils thus also need to be considered. Ti is also a good candidate due its high heat resistance. How thin the Ti foils can be made is a question. Then we have Mylar foils which can be made thinner <1 μm but it is less resistant to high temperature.

The goal of the test bench is to test foils of different thicknesses to see if they can withstand the pressure difference between the vacuum side and buffer gas side of the gas cell and to have minimum leak to the vacuum side. The test bench can help to develop a safe and reproducible protocol for mounting the windows. We aim to test windows of Al, Mylar, Aluminized Mylar and Titanium foils of different thicknesses. Possibility of using carbon foils (for thinner windows) will also be investigated. Also, viton and metallic O-rings for the window will be tested and their performances will be compared.

A frame needs to be built to support the foil and avoid damage while making screw holes for mounting the windows to the connecting part. The metallic foils are opaque and hence holes have to be made before mounting them. The mylar foils are transparent and the possibility of the making holes after mounting can be considered. Holes can also be made by melting the screw hole region with a soldering iron for Mylar foils.

Preliminary test bench

As preliminary test, entrance windows of Al 20 μm and Ti 5 μm were tested using a simplified test bench. The entrance window was mounted to an adapter piece which is the same window mounting support that will be used at S³. A connecting ring keeps the window in position to its mount. The window was pumped by a roughing pump from one side (corresponding to the S³ side) and the

other side was kept at atmospheric pressure (gas cell side) and leak tests were carried out. The pressure at the pumping side was measured over time to calculate the integral leak rate. Fig. 1a shows the window 3D design layout and fig. 1b shows the test bench.

Fig. 1 (a) Entrance window design. (b) Test bench layout.

Fig. 2 The measured leak rate for tested foils.

The integral leak rates obtained over time for different tests are shown in fig 2. Absolute pressure was measured manually at different points of time. The volume of the adapter piece along with the other connecting elements was estimated to have 6L. The leak rate was calculated by the equation:

$$Leak\ rate = \left(\frac{p_2 - p_1}{t_2 - t_1} \right) \times V \quad (1)$$

where p_2 , p_1 are the pressure at times t_1 and t_2 respectively, V is the total volume.

With the preliminary tests, we can conclude that the foils can withstand 1 bar pressure difference even with immediate evacuation. The mounting of the foils play a crucial role in the leak rate. The holes has to be precisely cut in the foils and then screw the connecting part to the mount. We tried several ways to screw in the connecting ring. Clamps were used to first hold the foil and the connecting part in position. Then the adapter side was pumped slowly. Once the foil was tight, screws were introduced to the previously made foil holes and slowly screwed in. The holes were made in the foil such that they coincide with the connecting ring screw holes. Other method was to directly screw in the foils without clamping it first and then slowly pumping. The second method worked well enough though it has a chance of forming small bumps near the connecting ring if not carefully mounted. This contributed to the leak which was observed when tested with a He leak detector. Other observation was that the grid made marks on the foil surface as it sticks close to the grid with pumping. This was not critical for the tested foils but can be a problem with thinner foils which has to be tested. Sand paper polishing was applied to make the sharper ends of the grid smoother to reduce damage of the foils. We also baked the window test chamber for the Al tests to see outgassing effects. The foil was baked under vacuum at a temperature of 125 °C for two days. There was a slight decrease in the leak rate as you can see from Al_test 2 compared to Al_test 1 from fig. 2.

The preliminary test bench implemented allowed us to validate that there are no faults on the machined pieces and establish a first installation protocol of the windows, which will be applied further on.

The S^3 gas cell conditions are different from the test bench. We cannot obtain the absolute the leak rate. Here the integral leak rate was measured from the pumping side with atmospheric pressure on the other side. As seen in the graph, this condition shows a sudden decrease in leak rate for the initial rate and slowly stabilizes.

The optimum procedure followed for the tests are mentioned stepwise:

- The foil is cut into rectangular piece in case of Al and the Ti foils are bought in the dimension 75 mm x 75 mm \pm 1 mm.

- The connecting ring of the window is used as a reference for making screw holes for the window
- The prepared foil is positioned with the screw holes on the window mount and screwed in carefully. Clamps can be used to hold the window in position with the mount.

- Once the screws are completely in, start pumping down one side of the window with the scroll pump.

- Tighten the screws gradually to have tighter seal. Be careful not to damage the foil by tightening too much.
- As you pump down, grid marks can be seen appearing on the window.

- Pump down until the limit of the scroll pump and then close the valve near to the pump as well as the window adapter volume.
- Measure the pressure, in the volume pumped down, time to time as it make significant rise.

- Calculate the leak rate as mentioned in the equation 1.

Developed test bench

To test the windows in the exact same conditions as the gas cell, a new test bench has to be prepared. In the new test bench, the purpose is to have a vacuum chamber instead of the gas cell, which can be injected with Ar gas as in the gas cell, to have a pressure of 200-500 mbar. The window mount is custom made and hence standard commercial chambers can't be used. We will use a bigger flange with a connecting flange custom drilled to accommodate the window dimensions. Fig. 3 shows a rough layout of the new test bench. In the figure, there is a 4-way cross to which Ar gas can be injected. The 4-way cross is mounted to a standard flange at the window side. The flange is drilled to attach to the window mount. We should be able to read the pressure at the gas cell side. Hence, a gauge should be connected to the side of the chamber. The other side of the window can be connected to the leak tester/mass spectrometer to measure leak and contribution of impurities from the O-rings used. Venting and pumping option at both side should also be possible. Unlike the previous test bench, instead of measuring the pressure rise, here we aim to measure the absolute pressure in the chamber. Leak detector can be connected to the pumping side. The test bench will be updated to read the pressure at the pumping side, remotely using LABVIEW program. The mounting procedure for window will be followed as in the previous test bench.

Fig. 3 New test bench layout.

Once all the foils are validated on the test bench, final tests will be performed with the window installed on the gas cell itself.